

Appraising the Legal Issues in Electronic Commercial Transactions in Nigeria

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Abstract:

The innovation of the internet through information communication technology has brought great development to commercial transactions in Nigeria and the global economy. It has paved the way for the expansion and publicity of business transactions. Electronic commercial transactions relate to commercial activities that deal with digital technology. These transactions rely on digital technology for effective performance and service delivery. Despite the adoption and recognition of electronic commercial transactions, issues such as dispute resolution, cyber security, and trust, among others, continue to undermine the effective performance of electronic commercial transactions. This study examined the nature of an electronic commercial transaction; its legal framework and the legal issues implicated by it. The study adopted the doctrinal legal research methodology. It relied on sources of data such as cases, statutes, books, journals, periodicals and internet materials. The study found that the growth of electronic commerce is hampered by some challenges, which have affected its widespread usage. The study however recommended the enactment of robust legislations that will promote the use and growth of electronic commercial transactions in the country.

Keywords: Electronic Commercial Transactions, Issues, Legal framework, Nigeria.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The internet has greatly improved from the conventional communication network such as the telephone network to more sophisticated interconnectivity of various networks.¹ Artificial intelligence, zoom, video conferencing among others have enhanced commercial activities both in Nigeria and across the globe.² It has a communication protocol where computers do not have to remain open while transactions are ongoing and where there is a system failure, the connection between the computers are not broken.³ The internet has created both local and international business relationship between consumers and businesses or vendors.

When compared with previous years, the present information communication technology that has ushered in commercial transactions over the internet, allows information to be transmitted promptly worldwide.⁴ An important component of internet is the website, which allows businesses to display their products and services. The website, through information technology, is the gateway to a successful business. Understandably, it projects a strong background for the company.⁵ Information technology is a useful tool for business transactions especially as a platform for electronic commercial transactions. However, despite the effectiveness of electronic commercial transactions in Nigeria, there are certain issues that affect their performance. In examining these issues, this study examines the meaning of electronic commercial transaction; explores the legal framework on electronic commercial transaction and the legal issues in electronic commercial transaction.

2. HISTORY, CONCEPT AND NATURE OF ELECTRONIC COMMERCIAL TRANSACTION

Historically speaking, electronic transaction otherwise known as e-commerce can be traced to the 1960s when companies began to use Electronic Data Interchange (EDI) for exchanging business letters and other documents.⁶ This era did not witness real business transactions but rather, it aided business transactions among companies. In the 1990s, Nigeria witnessed the emergence of e-commerce when the internet and telecommunications industry started becoming popular.⁷ However, the growth of e-

¹T Puurunen., 'Dispute Resolution in International Electronic Commerce' (Being PhD Dissertation submitted to University of Helsinki, Finland 2005) 3-4.

²P Butler and D Prasad., A Study of International Commercial Arbitration in the Commonwealth (Commonwealth Secretariat, 2020)9.

³Ibid.

⁴Ibid.

⁵Y ANanehkan., "An Introduction to Electronic Commerce" (2013) 2 (4) International of Scientific &Technology Research 192.

⁶ Andrew Bloomenthal. E-Commerce Defined: Types, History, and Examples. <http://investopedia.com/terms/e/commerce.asp>. accessed on the 4th May, 2025.

⁷T.I. Akomolede & M.S. Afolayan. Socio- Legal Analysis of Electronic Commercial Transactions in Nigeria. NAUJILJ Vol. 11 (2) 2020; 22.

commerce was retarded and limited until the Global System for Mobile Communication otherwise known as GSM was introduced to the general population. This brought tremendous expansion to the growth of e-commerce in Nigeria, and led to the establishment of online shopping platforms like Jumia and Konga. The growth of e-commerce was further accelerated with the introduction of online banking in the early 2000s.⁸

Electronic commercial transaction is a broad concept that deals with the buying and selling of goods and services by electronic means. It is a commercial transaction that adopts the use of information communication technology for convenient transactions and to serve a wider audience. The major tool of electronic commercial transaction is the use of the internet and computer network works through the innovation of information technology. Electronic commercial transaction is otherwise known as electronic commerce or e-commerce. It involves the use of internet in carrying out commercial activities.

The opportunities provided by the internet have contributed to the development of electronic commercial transactions across the globe.⁹ While an electronic commercial transaction is an entirely new way of doing business, it makes business activities convenient, effective and attractive.¹⁰ An emerging phenomenon deals with commercial transactions via the internet. Electronic commercial transaction has the ability to facilitate trade, improve the source of income and also contribute to the economic development of the country through the creation of job opportunities and export activities.¹¹

Furthermore, an electronic commercial transaction is limited to virtual communication, exchange of information or informatics products¹² and it entails the initiation and maintenance of websites whereby business organizations can deal and transact directly with consumers.¹³ The organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) defines electronic commercial transactions as commercial transactions involving both organizations and individuals, which are based on the processing and transmission of digitised data, including text, sound and visuals image

⁸ Ibid.

⁹J E Lawrence and U A Tar., 'Barriers to Ecommerce in Developing Countries' (2010)3(1) Information, Society and Justice, 23-35 at 23; M Tsagkias, H T King, S Kallumadi, et al., Challenges and Research Opportunities in eCommerce Search and Recommendations (2020)54(1), A paper delivered at the ACM SIGIR Forum 1-23 at 2. <http://sigir.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/p04.pdf> accessed 05 October 2024.

¹⁰J Iqbal, and F.A. Qazi., 'Challenges and Prospects of E-commerce in India' (2017)7(10) International Journal of Engineering Research and Application 14.

¹¹ R. Boateng, R Heeks, Molla andHinson., 'E-commerce and Socio-Economic Development: Conceptualizing the Link' (2008)18(5) InternetResearch562-564 at 577; Mohammed, D., 'E-commerce: Ongoing Challenges' (2010)15(2) Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce 1-4.

¹²M Alhamed., Electronic Arbitration as a Solution for Electronic Commerce Dispute Resolution in the United Arab Emirates: Obstacle and Enforceability Challenges (PhD University of Gloucestershire 2016)64

¹³C Chatterjee., E-commerce Law for Business Managers (Canterbury: Financial World Publishing, 2002)3

that are performed through open networks such as the internet.¹⁴ It is not limited to buying and selling of goods but includes the provision of services or information, which a business organization may offer to customers over the internet.¹⁵ It is used to reduce both transaction and production cost and it is often used as a marketing strategy for increase in sales.¹⁶ An electronic commercial transaction encompasses commercial activities that are facilitated through the internet in order to meet the needs of consumers.¹⁷

To Shahriari et al, it involves the use of computer network such as internet connectivity for the purpose of trading in goods and services (money transfer, marketing and supply).¹⁸ Due to the high competition provided by the internet, consumers get goods at lower price with numerous options.¹⁹ Leveraging electronic commercial transactions may result in technological improvement of developing countries.²⁰

Electronic commerce eradicates the need for face-to-face contact between the business and consumers, irrespective of their geographical locations.²¹ The electronic commercial transaction is often carried out through computer programs known as the websites. The programs reside in a computer known as “server”, and are maintained by Internet Service Providers (ISPs) or directly by business organizations who are parties to the transaction.²² With electronic commerce, sales, purchase and transportation of goods and services are performed with minimal effort and it also creates a relationship with the consumers and the business organizations.²³ Convenience, cost of products, availability of different brands of product have contributed to the rise in electronic commercial transaction.²⁴

Prior to the innovation and recognition of electronic commerce, the modes of communication such as electronic mails and telephones were used as tools for sending

¹⁴D Pallavi and A Tiwari., E-commerce-International Approach (2013) <<http://www.srdinodia.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/01/E-Commerce-International-Approach.pdf>> accessed 09 March 2024

¹⁵L Ahmed and R C Ogbu., E-commerce Problems and Prospects in Nigeria (2015)1(3) International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Applied Science 231

¹⁶Ibid.

¹⁷C Ferriter., ‘E-Commerce and International Commercial Arbitration’ (2001)1 University College Dublin Law Review, 51-66 at 51.

¹⁸S Shahriari, MShahriari, and S Gghriji., ‘E-commerce and its Impact on Global Trend and market’ (2015)3(4) International Journal of Research-Granthaalayah , 49-55 at 50.

¹⁹B H Malkawi., ‘E-commerce in Light of International Trade Agreements: The WTO and United States-Jordan Free Trade Agreement’ (2007)15(2) International Journal of Law and Information Technology 153-169

²⁰A G Khan., ‘Electronic Commerce: A Study on Benefits and Challenges in Emerging Economy’ (2016) 16(1) Global Journal of Management and Business Research: B Economics and Commerce 2.

²¹ UKEssays, A Brief History of E-commerce Information Technology (2018) <<https://www.ukessays.com/essays/information-technology/a-brief-history-of-e-commerce-information-technology-essay.php#citethis>> accessed 30 April 2024.

²²Ibid.

²³R Habibi and Z Hajati., ‘Trust in E-commerce’ (2015)10(3) International Journal of Innovation and Applied Studies 918.

²⁴A Reddy and M Jambulingam., ‘Online Dispute Resolution: A New Approach for E-commerce Dispute’ (2017)13(4) South East Asia Journal of Contemporary Business, Economics and Law 12.

structured and unstructured messages.²⁵ The use of websites and electronic communications to carry out business has reduced the cost of transactions connected to working with the use of paper, cost of storage and locating the place of purchase.²⁶ It has also eased the process of making inquiries about sales, price, and checking the availability of the product to be purchased through the use of online search engines such as, Google, ask.com among others. This is connected to the availability of electronic networks, applications, software, hardware and other communications network infrastructures.²⁷ An electronic commercial transaction draws on technologies such as mobile commerce, electronic transfer, supply chain management, internet marketing, online transaction processing, electronic data interchange, inventory management system and automated data collection systems.²⁸

3. LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR ELECTRONIC COMMERCIAL TRANSACTIONS

There are certain laws that regulate commercial transactions in Nigeria, and most of these laws did not envisage the possibility of electronic transaction when they were enacted. However, the reality of transactions initiated by digital technological innovation has emphasized the need for the enactment and amendment of laws to give effect to electronic commerce.

3.1 Nigerian Data Protection Act 2023

The Nigerian Data Protection Act 2023 replaced the Data Protection Regulation 2019. The Data Protection Act protects personal information and established the Nigeria Data Protection Commission, which regulates the processing of personal information. The commission helps in the implementation of the provisions of the Act. The essence of the Act is to further protect data and privacy rights as provided in the 1999 Constitution of the Federal republic of Nigeria.²⁹ In order to safeguard the personal information of consumers and businesses, the Act makes provision for the security of personal data and protection against unauthorized or unlawful data processing or any form of data breach.³⁰ The Act guarantees the safety of personal information and prohibits unauthorized access or data breach. It makes provision for instances where lawful data are processed with the consent of data subject for the performance of contracts, compliance with legal obligations, protection of vital interest of data subject, performance of tasks in the interest of the public and for other legitimate interests.³¹ Sensitive data of a data subject can only be processed based on the consent of the data subject for the specific purpose it is meant

²⁵Ibid.

²⁶Ibid.

²⁷C Fuchs and E Horak, 'Africa and the Digital Divide' (2008) 25 *Telematics and informatics* 99-116 at 101

²⁸Z Mengrui., 'Ethical Problems of International Electronic Commerce and Countermeasures' (2015) 2 (3) *European Journal of Business, Economics and Accountancy* 13.

²⁹T Ogele and S Akintola., 'Introducing the Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023' <https://www.aluko-oyebode.com/insights/nigeria-data-protection-act-2023-ndpa/> accessed 11 March 2025.

³⁰Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s24(1)(e).

³¹Ibid, 25(1).

for.³² This consent can be withdrawn by the data subject anytime it deems fit and he can also raise an objection against the processing of certain data relating to him.³³ In respect of the data transmitted for commercial purposes or any other purpose, the data controller and processor are expected to implement necessary technical and organizational measures to ensure integrity, security and confidentiality of data in their possession and protect it against any form of accident, loss, misuse and alteration.³⁴ This Act serves to protect personal information of consumers while engaging in business transactions with any business organisation or vendor.

3.2 Cyber Crime (Prohibition and Prevention) Act 2015

The Cyber Crime Act addresses acts relating to criminal activities in the cyberspace. It provides a comprehensive legal framework for the prohibition, prevention, detection and punishment of cyber-criminal activities in Nigeria. This Act protects innocent consumers from fraudulent activities while performing online business transactions. It protects consumers who engage in electronic transactions from any online criminal activities such as hacking, unauthorised access to computer and network infrastructure. The Act prohibits unauthorised access to computer systems or password for fraudulent purposes,³⁵ perpetration of electronic fraud,³⁶ computer system interference such as imputing, damaging, deleting, transmitting, suppressing and alteration of data,³⁷ destruction or abortion of electronic mails or processes with vital information which can be transmitted,³⁸ misdirection of electronic messages for fraudulent or financial gain,³⁹ unlawful interception of content, traffic data, electromagnetic emission or signal from computer or network by technical means,⁴⁰ unlawful access to computer network by altering any data with the intention to misrepresent information,⁴¹ loss of property by altering, suppressing, inputting, erasing any data in a computer for economic benefit,⁴² unauthorized modification of computer network or system,⁴³ fabrication of electronic tools,⁴⁴ breach of confidence by service provider or vendor through the illegal use of security codes of customer for financial gain or any other advantage.⁴⁵

³²Ibid, s30(1)(a)

³³Ibid, s35 and 36.

³⁴Ibid, s39.

³⁵Cybercrime (Prohibition and Prevention) Act 2015, s6.

³⁶Ibid, s7.

³⁷Ibid, s8.

³⁸Ibid, s9.

³⁹Ibid, s11.

⁴⁰Ibid, s12.

⁴¹Ibid, s13

⁴²Ibid, s14(1).

⁴³Ibid, s16(1)

⁴⁴Ibid, s28

⁴⁵Ibid, s29(1)

3.3 National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) Act 2007

The National Information Technology Development Agency Act (NITDA) 2007 is a law that regulates and promotes the use of information technology in Nigeria. NITDA established the National Information Technology Development Agency which is responsible for research, development, coordination, monitoring, evaluating and regulation of information technology practices and activities in Nigeria.⁴⁶ It introduced the Nigeria Data Protection Regulations (NDPR) 2019. The NDPR is applicable to organisations that handle data and engage in electronic commercial transactions. It mandates data controllers and processors to enforce technical and organisational protective measures on the security of personal data and prevent unauthorized access, disclosure or alternation.⁴⁷

NITDA developed an initiative known as the Nigeria Data Protection Compliance Organisation to facilitate compliance with the Nigeria Data Regulations through the provision of the support required to comply with with the regulations.⁴⁸ NITDA helps in maintaining customer data in the electronic commercial transaction industry through its institutional framework, that is, the National Information Technology Development Agency.

3.4 Evidence (Amendment) Act 2023

Prior to the enactment of the Evidence Act 2011, there were a lot of issues on the admissibility of electronically generated evidence because the repealed Evidence Act CapE14 2004 did not make provision for electronic evidence as same was not envisaged at the time it was enacted. The Evidence (Amendment) Act 2023 amends the Evidence Act 2011. This Act gives credence to the innovations of information communication technology and aligns the law of evidence with the current reality of digital and technological advancement. It has been amended to recognise and allow other forms of electronic evidence apart from electronic documents to be admitted in evidence.

The Evidence Act recognises and admits electronic data or electronic record of information. The Act makes any litigation relating to electronic commerce easy because it admits all computer-generated evidence or data. In other words, any information contained in an electronic record that is printed on a paper, stored, recorded, copied in any form by a computer is regarded as document and can be admitted in evidence.⁴⁹ Any electronic record of commercial transaction between a vendor and purchaser can be authenticated with digital signature of either of the parties producing it.⁵⁰ Where there

⁴⁶National Information Technology Development Agency Act (NITDA) 2007, s6.

⁴⁷Emerging Market Telecommunication Services v. Barr Godfrey Nya Eneye (2018) LPELR 46193

⁴⁸D Ikonne and G O Okorie, 'Scrutiny of the Legal and Regulatory Framework of E-commerce' (2023)13(1) Nigeria Bar Journal 21-53 at 36.

⁴⁹Evidence (Amendment) Act 2023, s84B.

⁵⁰Ibid, s84C.

are electronic evidential issues, this Act has been amended to take care of electronically generated evidence.

3.5 National Digital Economy and E-governance Act 2024

The essence of the National Digital Economy and E-governance Act 2024 is to promote Nigeria's economy through digital technology, improve service delivery and create an environment for electronic commercial transactions.⁵¹ The Act was also enacted to enhance digital transformation in public institutions, use digital innovations to provide legal framework to support international digital trade, and enhance digital economy governance amongst agencies, departments and ministries in Nigeria.⁵² The Act is applicable to public services institutions, private organisations, individuals, and organisations carrying out digital activities in Nigeria fully or partially.⁵³ It serves to promote the growth of digital economy and digital governance in Nigeria by promoting electronic transactions and other related services. The National Digital Economy and E-governance Act recognises and validates electronic commercial transactions in Nigeria. It recognises electronic communication in an electronic form; its legal effect, validity and admissibility,⁵⁴ and allows the use of automated message system for the formation of contractual relationship.⁵⁵

In the formation of contractual relationship or commercial transactions, offer and acceptance may be made through electronic communications.⁵⁶ An electronic communication of offer and acceptance is valid and enforceable. The time and place of dispatch of electronic communications is deemed to be the time the information leaves the information system of the sender or the time the electronic communication was received⁵⁷ while the time of receipt is the time when the electronic communication becomes capable of being retrieved by the recipient.⁵⁸ Invitation to treat or offer can be made through a proposal that is accessible to members of the public in one or more electronic communications without addressing it to a specific party.⁵⁹

The Act protects consumers' electronic commercial transactions by mandating the vendor to provide relevant or sufficient information (such as clear language understood by consumer, accurate information, display of stages of decision making of the consumer, business terms and conditions, description of goods and services, applicable currency, taxes, shipping charges, record of transaction and all other important information) on

⁵¹National Digital Economy and E-governance Act 2024, (Objectives).

⁵²Ibid.

⁵³Ibid, (Scope and application).

⁵⁴Ibid, s1.

⁵⁵Ibid, s4.

⁵⁶Ibid, s10.

⁵⁷Ibid, s12(1).

⁵⁸Ibid, s12(2).

⁵⁹Ibid, s13.

products and services to enable consumers make informed decision.⁶⁰ It offers consumer or vendors the opportunity to cancel the contract before orders are accepted or processed.⁶¹ In respect of the personal information of consumers during transactions, the vendor must ensure that all personal information are kept confidential except where the consumer consents to the disclosure of his personal information. However, the private policy of the vendor must be displayed for easy accessibility.⁶² Any vendor using electronic communications such as the various social media platforms to sell goods and services to consumers must provide accurate clear and accessible information about himself, the description of the goods or services, and associated cost among others.⁶³ For the security of electronic commercial transaction, the National Insurance Commission (NAICOM) is responsible for the provision of cyber-insurance.⁶⁴

4. LEGAL ISSUES IN ELECTRONIC COMMERCIAL TRANSACTIONS

Information technology has brought great transformations to the conduct of commercial transactions across the globe.⁶⁵ Despite the benefits of electronic commerce, there are a number of issues associated with it.⁶⁶ The issues are examined below.

4.1 Choice of Applicable Law

The choice of law or the applicable law is an essential part of any contractual agreement due to the eventuality of disputes arising between the parties. In the case of electronic commercial transactions, the law to be applied by the parties is often a subject of concern due to the rapid movement of data and dispersed locations implicated.⁶⁷ Most of the laws on commercial transaction in Nigeria and across the globe did not envisage the possibility of electronic commercial transactions, thereby creating loopholes and certain inadequacies when issues relating to electronic commercial transaction disputes arise.⁶⁸ Consequently, the existing legislation on commercial transactions is inadequate.⁶⁹

Another issue affecting the effectiveness of electronic commercial transaction is that even when the laws are enacted, they cannot meet all the demands of disputing parties because of the likelihood of emerging technological innovation that was not

⁶⁰Ibid, s36.

⁶¹Ibid, s37.

⁶²Ibid, s38.

⁶³Ibid, s39.

⁶⁴Ibid, s40.

⁶⁵T Kaushal, and J K Jain., 'Emerging Challenges of Global E-Commerce'(2017) 2(3) International Journal of Advanced Research 7-11 at 7.

⁶⁶S Khan., 'Legal Issue in E-commerce' (2018) 4.

<https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/cefact/cf_forums/2018_China/eCommerce_Bio-PPT/PPT_10Khan.pdf> accessed 31 December 2024.

⁶⁷M Nuruddeen., Legal Issues in Electronic Commerce: Challenges and Prospects for Nigeria (2014) <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/316736921> accessed 05 October 2024.

⁶⁸Ibid.

⁶⁹Ibid.

envisaged when the laws were drafted.⁷⁰ For instance, in the cases of *Nuba Commercial Farms Ltd vs. NAL Bank Ltd*⁷¹ and *UBA Plc vs. S.A.F.P.U*⁷² the court refused to rely on computer generated evidence because the old Evidence Act did not make provisions for it. However, shortly after the amendment of the Evidence Act 2011, courts have now recognized the relevance of electronic evidence as for example, in the case of *Kubor and Anor vs. Dickson and Anor*.⁷³

This challenge is not peculiar to Nigeria as some other countries also encountered it due to the absence of a bespoke legislative framework on electronic evidence. For instance, when issues relating to computer-generated evidence came up in the United Kingdom, the court adopted the best evidence rule in the interest of justice.⁷⁴ Also, in the United States' case of *King vs. State Ex Rel Murdock Acceptance Corporation*, the court extended the exception to hearsay evidence to computer generated evidence while admitting the document in the interest of justice.⁷⁵

4.2 Data Protection

One of the main issues in electronic commerce transactions is data protection. This is because e-commerce transactions make use of both sensitive and non-sensitive data of consumer that must be protected from being used in a manner detrimental to the data subject. The security of electronic data and the prevention of unauthorized access are vital in electronic commercial transactions because it deals with information technology.⁷⁶ Protection of data and easy accessibility of the internet often threatens the security of commercial transactions.⁷⁷ Data protection deals with the safety of the right to privacy as protected by the constitution of Nigeria, the Data Protection Act, and international conventions. Legislations have been passed to protect collected, stored or processed information.⁷⁸

Data protection is an essential issue in electronic commercial transactions, which forms part of the contractual relationship and agreement of the parties. The personal data disclosed to business organizations by consumers are of immense value and should be protected by the organization. In other words, the personal data of consumers provided

⁷⁰Nuruddeen(n 67) 6.

⁷¹ (2001) 16 NWLR (Pt.340) at 523.

⁷² (2004) 3 NWLR (Pt. 861) 523.

⁷³ (2013)3 NWLR (Pt. 1182) 564 at 585.

⁷⁴ Best evidence rule is a common law principle that allows evidence to be admitted if such evidence is the best evidence available to prove a particular case.

⁷⁵ (1996) 22 F2d 39.

⁷⁶ T Castleman, P A Swatman, and M P Craig., 'Issues in the Implementation of Electronic Commerce in the Human Services: Reflections on the Victorian Initiatives (1999) 1-12 at 8 <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.46.4390&rep=rep1&type=pdf> accessed 27 November 2024.

⁷⁷ T I Akomolede., 'Contemporary Legal Issues in Electronic Commerce in Nigeria' (2008)11 Potchefstroom Electronic Law Journal 1-24 at 3.

⁷⁸ Explainer, 101: Data Protection (2017) <<https://privacyinternational.org/explainer/41/101-data-protection>> accessed 07 February 2024.

over the internet are of great importance to the organization and must be safeguarded.⁷⁹ The Data Protection Act 2023 serves to protect the data and personal information of consumers in electronic commercial transactions. However, because it is a recent enactment, it has not totally eradicated the breach of consumer privacy.

There are several conventions on the protection of information provided by consumers. For instance, the European Convention on Protection of Personal Data 1981, and the OECD Guidelines on the Protection of Privacy and Transborder Flows of Personal Data which was adopted in 1980 guarantee the confidentiality of communications, protection of legal persons and the content of electronic communication, provision of security for information provided and the extent of the secrecy.⁸⁰ Express usage of consumer information for other purposes outside a commercial transaction must be subjected to the consent of the consumer.

Internet fraudsters may tamper with consumer data not guaranteed by the business organization the consumer is dealing with.⁸¹ All sensitive information such as financial details, ethnic background, sexual health, belief, criminal record, political opinion must be protected by the business organization.⁸² The need for data privacy and its challenges were emphasized in the case of *R v. Brown*, where the court that:

Vast amount of information about everyone are stored on computers, capable of instant transmission anywhere in the world and accessible at the touch of a keyboard. The right to keep oneself to oneself, to tell other people that certain things are none of their business is under technological threat.⁸³

4.3 Formation of Virtual Contract

A virtual contract is an agreement made over the internet. Notwithstanding the fact it is an online agreement between parties, it must contain all the essential requirements of a valid contract such as offer, acceptance, capacity, consideration and intention to create legal relationship.⁸⁴ An agreement may be entered into electronically through various means such as email, electronic data interchange, listserv and chats services, social media platforms and World Wide Web interfaces.⁸⁵ Electronic data interchange (EDI) involves the transfer of information between a number of computer networks. EDI assumes that a business relationship already exists between the parties.⁸⁶ There must be an acceptance of the offer made i.e. when received, consensus must be reached and parties to the

⁷⁹ Castleman, Swatman and Craig (n76) 8

⁸⁰Ibid.

⁸¹S N Sinha, G Tanty and R P Panigrahi., 'E-commerce & M-Commerce Growth, Issues & Challenges in India' (2019)8(12) International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research 2970-2974 at 2971.

⁸² Data Protection Act 1998, s16.

⁸³ (1996) 1 All 545, 556.

⁸⁴A M Al Masadeh, A M Khawaldeh and M A Al-salamat., 'The Electronic Contract in Civil and Commercial Code' (2024)18(1) International Journal of Cyber Criminology 1-14 at 3-4.

⁸⁵Ibid

⁸⁶A G Mirzaian., ' YsK ... Who Cares? We Have Bigger Problems: Choice of Law in Electronic Contract' (2000)6(4) Richmond Journal of Law and Technology. 1-48 at 7.

contract, who may be natural or artificial persons.⁸⁷ Acceptance may be communicated to the offeror through fax,⁸⁸ telephone⁸⁹ and telex.⁹⁰

On the other hand, the nature of virtual contract differs from the conventional contract because it is often difficult to differentiate when the electronic business is making an offer or an invitation to treat.⁹¹ However, when an offer is made *via* electronic mail, acceptance is made and stated in the reply as the mere receipt of such mail will not constitute an acceptance.⁹² The element of consideration is satisfied where the consumer saves the item in a cart or promises to pay at a later date while contractual intention is established in the course of interaction with automated machines.⁹³ The National Digital Economy and E-governance Act 2024 being a recent enactment, now recognises electronic contract and commercial transactions.⁹⁴

4.4 Jurisdictional and Evidential Issues

Issues may arise in electronic commercial transactions on jurisdictional and evidential matters. These are prevalent matters in electronic commercial transactions because transactions are performed across borders. As soon as the contracting parties in different jurisdictions enter into a virtual contract and dispute arises thereafter between the parties, the choice of a forum and choice of law to determine the jurisdiction where the dispute will be heard and the applicable law is vital.⁹⁵ In terms of jurisdiction of the parties, party autonomy is a distinctive feature.⁹⁶ One of the relevant Conventions on jurisdiction is the Brussel Convention on Jurisdiction and Enforcement of Judgment in Civil and Commercial Matters.⁹⁷ Jurisdiction is determined by the place where the commercial transaction is performed, but if it is performed in different jurisdictions, the appropriate jurisdiction will be the place where the dispute arose.⁹⁸

As previously state, electronic commercial transactions are paperless transactions made via the internet with the parties in different locations or geographical boundaries. All information relating to such transactions are displayed on the company's or business organization's website. Evidential issues may arise in respect of the proof of transaction performed over the internet and electronic communications, and information posted

⁸⁷Ibid at 114.

⁸⁸Joan Balcom Sales Inc. v. Poirier (1991) 49 C.P.C (2d) 180 (N.S. Co.Ct)

⁸⁹Re Viscount Supply Co. (1963) 1 O. R 640 (S.C)

⁹⁰Entores Ltd v. Miles Far East Corp., (1955) 2 Q.B. 327 (C.A)

⁹¹Akomolade(n 77) 5.

⁹²Ibid at 6.

⁹³Ibid.

⁹⁴National Digital Economy and E-governance Act 2024, s10 and s13.

⁹⁵L E Gilles., *Electronic Commerce and International Private Law: A Study of Electronic Consumer Contracts* (UK Ashgate Publishing Limited 2008)3.

⁹⁶C FuhKwanga., 'Electronic Commerce in Cameroon: An Appraisal of Legal Issues and Challenges' (2018) *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science* 47.

⁹⁷1958. This Convention is only applicable to countries that have ratified and incorporated the Convention into their local legislations.

⁹⁸ Akomolede (n 77) 9.

online may be corrupted or deleted or altered by hackers.⁹⁹ On the admissibility of data and information, Article 9 of the UNCITRAL Model Law on Electronic Commerce preserves the admissibility and legal weight of data messages in legal proceedings despite the fact that they are in an electronic form.¹⁰⁰ Information generated, stored, sent or received by electronic mail, telex or telegrams are admissible data, and evidential weight can be attached to them by virtue of the Evidence (Amendment) Act 2023.¹⁰¹

4.5 Market Competition

Market competition is a prevalent phenomenon in commercial transactions. While electronic commercial transactions are not left out, business organizations often take some measures to meet up with existing market competition by distinguishing themselves from other market competitors in order to gain the attention of new customers.¹⁰² This is often made possible because of the reliance on information technology today. Information technology has increased the competitiveness of virtual commercial transactions due to the introduction of new applications and services via the internet, and where there is a market competition among online businesses, consumers are always at an advantaged position of getting goods at a lower price.¹⁰³

The rapid growth of virtual commercial transactions has brought vast competition to the electronic market.¹⁰⁴ Business organizations that offer promotional, competitive market, strong brand image, quick response time, and entertaining websites among others may rise above competition in the virtual commercial transaction domain.¹⁰⁵ However, hackers may take advantage of this market competition in hacking the accounts of vendors or businesses to defraud or tamper with the personal information of consumers for financial benefits.

4.6 Dispute Resolution

Disputes are inevitable aspects of commercial transactions. However, the need to resolve such disputes is vital to the maintenance of the relationship between business organizations and consumers, especially when it is based on contractual obligations.¹⁰⁶ Dispute also occur in electronic commercial transactions as customers may for example, be aggrieved in respect of products and services or the suitability of the product delivered.¹⁰⁷

⁹⁹FuahKwanga(n 96) 47.

¹⁰⁰ UNCITRAL Model Law 1996, art 9(2).

¹⁰¹Ibid art 2.

¹⁰² J Post., Top E-Commerce Challenges Facing SMBs. August 04, 2019. <https://www.businessnewsdaily.com/6028-small-ecommerce-challenges.html> accessed 10 October 2024.

¹⁰³ P Tang, D J Powell, K Worlock, and J Bingham., The Impact of Electronic Commerce on the Competitiveness of SMEs in the EU (European Parliament, 2000)1-83 at 9.

¹⁰⁴Ibid

¹⁰⁵ C Sahin., 'Competitiveness of E-Commerce Companies: An Integrated Approach' (2012)4(1) International Journal of e-Business and e-Government Studies 13-22 at 16.

¹⁰⁶ UNCTAD, E-commerce and the Development Report (United Nations 2001) https://unctad.org/en/Docs/ecdr2001_en.pdf accessed 04 April 2024.

¹⁰⁷FuahKwanga(n 96) 49.

Parties to a transaction may resort to the traditional or adversarial mode of resolving disputes. Alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms such as arbitration, conciliation, mediation, and so on, play important role in resolving disputes. Adversarial dispute resolution process has to do with applicable rules relied on by the parties, to govern their transaction and relationship but arbitration is often preferred due to its flexibility, convenience and speed as opposed to the adversarial process that is rigid, expensive and time consuming. In traditional or conventional arbitration, the rules adopted by the parties must be based on their mutual agreement. Besides litigation, there is a need for a suitable means of dispute resolution that would address the peculiarities of virtual commercial transactions.

Online dispute resolution can fit into virtual transaction disputes because disputing parties do not have to meet physically before their disputes are resolved. They can resolve their dispute at their own convenience.¹⁰⁸ Online business organizations are expected to design a software for resolution of disputes arising in the course of commercial activities performed over the internet, while making litigation their last resort.¹⁰⁹ This online dispute resolution process such as virtual arbitration is convenient, fast, cost effective non-confrontational, confidential and easily accessible notwithstanding the geographical boundaries of the parties. It is a way of securing the trust and confidence of consumers in electronic commercial transactions.¹¹⁰

4.7 Cyber Security

Security is an important issue in electronic business transactions. Security determines the growth or otherwise of electronic commercial transactions.¹¹¹ Cyber security is important in virtual transactions to protect commercial transactions from cyber-attacks. It also prevents any attack on vital data or information and digital infrastructure,¹¹² and makes sure that personal information or data are not tampered with by unauthorized users.¹¹³

The initiators of electronic commercial transactions are often not aware of any background activities going on when they are performing transactions over the internet.¹¹⁴ Some of these background events may alter vital information or data. This often occurs due to the weak cybersecurity infrastructure in place. Despite the enactment of the Cyber Crime Act in 2015, the Cyberspace remains susceptible to the breach of data or personal

¹⁰⁸ O Olumide., *Dispute Resolution Techniques in E-commerce Transaction* (2017). 1-27 at 6. <https://www.academia.edu> accessed 05 October 2024.

¹⁰⁹ *Ibid.*

¹¹⁰ *Ibid.*

¹¹¹ N Kitukutha., and J Olah., 'Trust and E-Commerce, Case Study on Jumia Company' (2018) *The Annals of the University of Oradea. Economic Sciences.* 313-323.

¹¹² J Post., *Top E-commerce Challenges Facing SMBs* (2019) <https://www.businessnewsdaily.com/6028-small-e-commerce-challenges.html> accessed 05 October, 2024.

¹¹³ Z Mustata, D Aziz and M S Abu Hassan., *E-Commerce Challenges and Solutions* (2016) 1-5 at 3. <http://E-CommerceChallengesandSolutions.pdf> 05 October 2024.

¹¹⁴ M A Nasir., *Legal Issues Involved in E-Commerce* (2004) <https://www.id.acm.org> accessed 08 February 2025.

information. Nevertheless, some security measures may prevent it from being tampered with.¹¹⁵ Security is more important to the consumer because the consumer provides personal data and financial information for goods and services rendered.¹¹⁶ Security issues have the possibility of preventing consumers and business organizations from engaging in electronic commercial transactions.¹¹⁷ Susceptibility to attacks from internet fraudsters is one of the barriers facing electronic commercial transactions.¹¹⁸ One of the issues relating to cyber security is the need to verify (identity verification) whether the seller is authentic before making payment for products ordered, in order to avoid making payment to fraudulent account.¹¹⁹ To curb this menace, electronic security must secure information on the internet.

Electronic security protects data and infrastructure from unlawful usage, unlawful access, security threats and destruction.¹²⁰ Denial-of-service (DoS) attacks, virus attacks, cybersquatting are some of the security threats in electronic commercial transactions.¹²¹ Another security threat is posting of spams and dangerous viruses to infect vital data thereby corrupting the website and disrupting commercial transactions.¹²² Hackers may also hack into the website to steal vital and confidential information from the website of businesses, thereby causing huge financial losses.¹²³ The rapid expansion of electronic commercial transactions has exposed many consumers to security threat.¹²⁴ The safety and privacy of consumer in the course of performing virtual transactions lies with the business organization a consumer is dealing with. In other words, there should be an assurance by the organization about the safety of the information provided by consumers.¹²⁵

Software bugs also threaten the security of electronic commercial transactions. These bugs are introduced to cause the computer program to malfunction or to crash the

¹¹⁵ The Future of ODR: The Promise of Advancing Technology (2015) <<https://mttlr.org/2015/10/the-future-of-odr-the-promise-of-advancing-technology/>> accessed 03 February 2025.

¹¹⁶ M M Cruz-Cunha and J. Varejao ., E-business Issues, Challenges and Opportunities for SMEs driving Competition (2011) 335-349 at 339. <https://bibliotecadigital.ipb.pt/bitstream/10198/3620/1/Ch.%2019%20Publicado.pdf> accessed 05 October 2021.

¹¹⁷ S W Khan., Cyber Security Issues and Challenges in E-Commerce (2015) 1197-1204 at 1198. <http://www.ssrn.com> accessed 08 October 2024.

¹¹⁸ Ibid.

¹¹⁹ N Bika., 10 E commerce Challenges Businesses Face [+Easy Solution] 2021 <https://acquire.io/blog/ecommerce-challenges/> accessed 06 October 2024.

¹²⁰ M Niranjnamurthy., N Kavyashree., S Jagannath and DChahar., Analysis of E-Commerce and M-Commerce: Advantages, Limitations and Security Issues (2013)2(6) International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering, 2360-2370 at 2369.

¹²¹ M Nikam and J Rokade., 'Data Privacy, Trust Issues and Solutions in Electronic Commerce' (2020)7(3) International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology 3961-3964 at 3961.

¹²² Niranjnamurthy et'al (n 120).

¹²³ Kaur, A., Top 10 eCommerce Challenges and Easy Ways to Overcome them (2021) <https://www.netsolutions.com/insights/ecommerce-business-challenges-and-solutions/> accessed 05 October 2024.

¹²⁴ R K Mahajan., Security Issues and Guideline for a Successful E-Commerce System (2018)5(2) International Journal of Research and Analytical Review 1837-1840 at 1838.

¹²⁵ Nasir (n 114) 4.

software.¹²⁶ Other means of hacking into the system may involve introducing software into to the system of another person and instructing it to send requests to targets simultaneously.¹²⁷

4.8 Trust

Trust is another important issue in electronic commercial transactions. The quantum of trust required in the conventional commercial transactions is lower than electronic commercial transaction because consumers have access to only the pictures or images of goods. Some consumers avoid electronic commercial transactions due to lack of trust and the concept of what I ordered versus what I got.¹²⁸ Trust in commercial transactions determines the success or failure of the business organization, and absolute trust must be displayed in all phases of the commercial transaction.¹²⁹ Some of the factors used by commercial businesses to gain consumer's trust are quality of service, appearance of the websites, branding and quality of products.¹³⁰ Consumers are skeptical when performing virtual transactions due to issues relating to their financial security and the credibility of the business organization.¹³¹ Consumers find it difficult to connect individuals with activities performed over the internet because it is not a face-to-face transaction.¹³²

Trust in commercial transactions is indispensable. It is not an entitlement, as it must be earned and maintained throughout the transaction.¹³³ It is not necessary for the business organization to create the impression of trustworthiness because other activities that affect its reputation might happen beyond its control.¹³⁴ Trust is an important necessity in electronic commerce or trading. It is usually taken seriously in the virtual world than the real world because parties performing the transaction merely rely on information without meeting each other physically.¹³⁵ Being a vital aspect of human relationship, trust is based on what an individual perceives about the online market.¹³⁶

¹²⁶A Toleuuly, Yessengeldin B, Jumabaeva S, and Zhanseitov A., 'Contemporary Problems and Prospects of e-Commerce Development in Modern Conditions' (2019)40(7) *RevistaEspacios* 24-29 at 27.

¹²⁷M Sopotkamon., *E-commerce challenges and issues* (2006) 1-36 at 15. https://cpe.ku.ac.th/~mcs/docs/E-Commerce_talk.pdf accessed 05 October 2024.

¹²⁸M Gustavsson and A Johansson., *Consumer Trust in E-commerce* (2006)1-61 at 21. <http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:230780/FULLTEXT01.%20%20%20%20%20%20%20%20%20%20.pdf> accessed 10 October 2024.

¹²⁹*Ibid.*

¹³⁰S Manivannan., 'Security and Trust in e-Business: Problems and Prospects' (2009) *Journal of e-Business* 66-102 at 66.

¹³¹P Domadenik., M Koman., and K Redek., *Shaping the Future: Opportunities and Challenges of E-commerce* (Casnik Finance, 2018)1-248 at 31.

¹³² Gustavsson and Johansson (n 128).

¹³³A Adegoke., *Challenges of E-commerce in Nigeria and Solutions* (2018) <https://hintng.com/challenges-of-e-commerce-in-nigeria-and-solutions/> accessed 05 October 2024.

¹³⁴ Gustavsson and Johansson (n 128) 26.

¹³⁵ J E Lawrence and A Tar., 'Barrier to Ecommerce in Developing Countries' (2010)3(1) *Information, Society and Justice*, 23-35 at 28.

¹³⁶ Gustavsson and Johansson (n 128) 24.

Trust is a strategy used by consumers to minimize the insecurity and intricacy of electronic commercial transactions because they do not have face-to-face contact with the business organization and the product.¹³⁷ The reputation, customer satisfaction, integrity and enticing website may sometime earn the trust of consumers.¹³⁸ The techniques that can be used to promote internet trust are detailed information on the use of the website, friendly marketing strategy, effective communication, transparency and adequate protective measures.¹³⁹ Business organizations must protect at all times, the sensitive data of users.¹⁴⁰ Sometimes, consumers want to be assured and be in control of their personal information, and when this is guaranteed, they trust such organization.¹⁴¹ Some of the challenges associated with trust in virtual transactions are delivery of counterfeit products, change of contractual terms, late delivery, and non-delivery after payments have been made.¹⁴² Other trust related issues are fraudulent activities of sellers and lack of transparency.

4.9 Taxation of Electronic Transactions

Another legal issue in electronic transaction is taxation. There is no doubt that electronic transactions are gaining prominence despite the challenges associated with them. This has reduced the rate of conventional commercial transactions and has affected the tax revenue derived from conventional transactions. To this end, there is the need for government to establish a legal framework to address the taxation of commercial transactions done electronically. In response to the above, the Nigerian government promulgated the Finance Act 2019, which has been amended several times.

The Companies Income Tax Act was also amended to respond to the taxation of electronic transactions. One of the key innovations in these laws is to include in the tax net, online businesses that derive income in Nigeria through the principle of significant economic presence (SEP).¹⁴³ Although, complicating the issue of the multiplicity of taxation, the new tax policy has successfully addressed the issue of tax evasion occasioned by e-commerce transactions, and has brought within the tax net, companies or businesses that derive their income from Nigeria, or which have a significant economic presence in Nigeria.

¹³⁷M Falahat, Y Lee, Y Foo, and C Chia., 'A Model for Consumer Trust in E-Commerce' (2019)24 Asian Academy of Management Journal 93-109 at 94.

¹³⁸Y Fang, I Qureshi, H Sun, P McCole, E Ramsey, and K H Lim., 'Trust, Satisfaction and online Repurchase Intention: The Moderating Role of Perceived Effectiveness of E-Commerce Institutional Mechanisms' (2014) MIS Quarterly 407-427.

¹³⁹Gustavsson and Johansson (n 128) 27.

¹⁴⁰Manivannan (n 130).

¹⁴¹Ibid.

¹⁴²Ibid.

¹⁴³Companies Income Tax Act C21 LFN 2004, s13(2) which was amended by Section 4 of the Finance Act, 2020.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Electronic commercial transactions play a vital role in enhancing commercial activities and providing a convenient atmosphere for consumers to perform commercial transaction within the comfort of their homes. With the innovation of information communication technology, electronic commercial transactions have become a norm both in Nigeria and across the globe. Although most laws regulating commercial activities and evidential issues were enacted before the emergence of information communications technology, and without envisaging its development, information technology has led to the enactment of laws to accommodate information technology and its innovations. Despite the enactment of these laws, electronic commercial transactions are still confronted with certain issues. This study however recommends that there should be adequate security measures in place to enhance the security of information transmitted in the cyberspace so as to protect the data of the consumer and the e-commerce company. There should be a strong legal framework on electronic commercial transactions that can enhance the growth of commercial transactions and implementation of strict cybersecurity laws to prevent fraudulent activities. Finally, there should be periodic public awareness and enlightenment campaigns on the prevention of fraudulent online activities.